

THE MAIN PRINCIPLES OF TEACHING "MUSIC THEORY" IN SPECIALIZED MUSIC SCHOOLS

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Abstract. *This article describes the main principles of teaching "music theory" in specialized music schools, the theory of music teaching methodology and the goals of the school repertoire course.*

Key words: *methodology, teaching, music, school, repertoire, theory.*

ОСНОВНЫЕ ПРИНЦИПЫ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ «ТЕОРИИ МУЗЫКИ» В СПЕЦИАЛИЗИРОВАННЫХ МУЗЫКАЛЬНЫХ ШКОЛАХ.

Аннотация. *В статье описаны основные принципы преподавания «теории музыки» в специализированных музыкальных школах, теория методики преподавания музыки и цели школьного репертуарного курса.*

Ключевые слова: *методика, преподавание, музыка, школа, репертуар, теория.*

In strengthening the foundations of our independence, and in the transformation of Uzbekistan into a great country, one of the most urgent tasks is the proper implementation of educational work. Because science, culture and spirituality elevate any country and nation to the heights, ensure its development, and predict its future. The subject "Music teaching methodology, theory and school repertoire" as a pedagogic subject summarizes all the parts of the experimentally tested work and presents the methods of music teaching that have given effective results in practice. The methodology is mainly based on the research results of pedagogy, psychology, aesthetics and art science. He describes the rules of music education and defines the modern technologies and methods used in the education of the young generation in the future. The science of methodology refers to the content of the teacher's methods of working with students in the educational process. The science of "music teaching methodology, theory and school repertoire" is not a science that was formed suddenly, but a science that has its own historical development path. In Uzbekistan, great thinkers, scientists, experienced teachers, methodologists, local scientists contributed to the formation of methodical science by creating their own research works, studies, experimental works, pamphlets, opinions, educational programs and textbooks. contributors.

The purpose of the course "Music Teaching Methodology, Theory and School Repertoire" as a subject is to prepare students for the practical work of a future music teacher, as well as equip them with methodological knowledge and skills. Achieving this goal requires long creative work during practical training. It is known that the school uses the theory and methodology of music education depending on the young psychological and physiological characteristics of the students.

Here, the educational method, educational principles of educational materials (curriculum, program), goals and tasks of educational work are of great importance. The word "methodology"

comes from the Greek word *boii*, which means "the way of research", "the way of knowing". The methods of teaching music are the working methods used by schoolchildren to acquire knowledge, skills and abilities.

The main tasks of the "Music teaching methodology and school repertoire" course are as follows:

- to have an idea about the culture of the individual in the educational system;
- study of the reforms being carried out in the field of education, the demands placed on a modern teacher;
- use of modern technologies in the preparation of lesson plans;
- to be able to use methodological developments, visual aids, preparation of handouts, computer, slides, discs, magnetic tapes,
- to apply music teaching methods and methods in accordance with the age of each class;
- shaping the musical culture and spirituality of the future generation through the medium of music;
- learning the methods of formation and organization of musical education outside the classroom and school;
- conducting experimental tests in pedagogical practice;
- holding meetings with well-known composers, poets, artists, participating in contests, forming the education of sophistication among students;
- studying the education system of foreign countries;
- organization of cooperation activities between teacher and student;
- completing the assigned task on time and thoroughly preparing for practical trainings and seminars;
- independent work with recommended literature;
- teaching students to think independently, research, study, draw conclusions;
- to increase the creative activity of students in the process of independent work;
- practical training is a logical continuation of lectures, teaching students to strengthen the knowledge acquired during lectures.

The subject "Music teaching methodology, theory and school repertoire" is considered a general professional subject and includes pedagogy, psychology, school repertoire practice, speech culture, music history, solo singing, conducting, musical instrument, solfeggio, choral music theory, children's literature, Pedagogical skills are closely related to subjects such as mother tongue, literature, and nature. These musical theoretical sciences will help teachers to effectively convey the art of music to children, to teach them how life is reflected in musical images, and to use musical means of expression in practice.

These subjects are closely related to each other and help the students to develop their spiritual and moral education and master musical science thoroughly. This will teach the future teachers how to effectively convey the secrets of musical art to students.

Music culture lessons are organized based on didactic theory and principles of pedagogy.

These principles determine the basic requirements of all educational principles - lesson content methods and the structure of the lesson and its directions, performed by the teacher and the student. The didactic principles of music culture classes consist of five types:

1. The principle of systematicity, scientificity and continuity in music education and training.
2. The principle of student awareness and activity in the lesson.
3. Demonstration principle in musical culture classes.
4. The principle of matching educational materials to children's abilities and skills.
5. The principle of continuity of knowledge and skills in music lessons. These principles are mainly used in the process of using educational materials, creating the content and plan of music lessons. The above-mentioned universal didactic principles are inextricably linked with each other and ensure the consistency of music activities based on the continuity and integrity of the music lesson in accordance with the state educational standard, taking into account the national characteristics.

1. The principle of systematicity, scientificity and continuity in music education and training should be established on a scientific basis in each lesson with its own structure and content. The scope of knowledge about music is the main factor of music education and upbringing. It reflects the rules, conclusions, and generalized musical experiences of music created by mankind. Mastering them means acquiring knowledge and skills in the way of musical practice.

Adaptation of educational materials to the knowledge experience of the child during the lesson. Taking into account the laws of children's voice development, teaching the laws of notes correctly, and analyzing them in accordance with the child's intellectual abilities are the scientific principles of the lesson. It is difficult to implement science without a system. All educational activities of the lesson and the interrelationship of subsequent lessons form the basis of the system.

The principles of mastering works from simple to complex, from unknown to known are consistent with a certain order, which means systematicity. The principle of continuity means that each activity of the lesson, in turn, is a logical continuation of each lesson and gradually realizes the pedagogical goals.

2. The principle of awareness and activity of students in the lesson. This principle is one of the leading principles of didactics. Because the acquisition of knowledge depends on the cognitive process that is the basis of the student's actual activity. Music perception enriches a person's life experience, increases the ability to perceive, think and perceive real events artistically.

The formation of these skills and abilities requires a long process of development of the child's mind. For this purpose, the child's conscious learning of learning material creates the activity of the learning process. Mastering a certain piece of music by singing or listening to it and enjoying it artistically, aesthetically, enjoying it, attracting the attention of the child, first of all, creates interest, consciousness and activity in it.

3. It requires conscious perception of music and, in turn, artistic tone and logical retention in memory. Awareness and activity in music lessons are especially necessary for the formation of vocal and choral skills. Singing in a choir, listening to music, music literacy, awareness and activity in activities make it easier to know and master the theoretical and practical aspects of music. 3. Demonstration principle in music lessons. In music education, music itself is a self-explanatory tool. Because it is perceived not by the eyes, but by the ears. Both in listening to music and in the analysis of the work, the melody is performed as an exhibition. the teacher himself, speech, and performance serve as the main exhibition. In addition, technical tools, flash

cards, graphic records, pictures, sheet music play an important role as an exhibition in music lessons.

4. The principle of compatibility of educational materials with educational needs. This principle is used in the process of creating the content of the lesson based on the educational materials recognized by the program and the methodological materials. It is necessary to take into account the general knowledge and skill level of each class. Based on the program, taking into account the knowledge and skills of each class, a half-yearly calendar-thematic plan of the music lesson is drawn up. A calendar - a thematic work plan is drawn up twice a year, depending on the age characteristics of the student, musical studies, new songs, works for listening to music, educational materials in music literacy, and class activities. 5. Consolidation of knowledge and skills in music lessons. The main condition for the implementation of these principles is to seriously follow the four principles described above. First of all, it is necessary to ensure the depth, solidity and vitality of knowledge and skills, that is, it is necessary to make children confident that this asami and its performance method are necessary for our cultural life. Secondly, when choosing an asariami, the following should be followed: a) suitability of the asariami for the spiritual and moral education of the child. b) nature of music education. c) to be able to interest all children in the class in this work and achieve full mastery. Thirdly, repetition and strengthening of the range of knowledge and skills acquired in the lesson in practice. Masai an: Teaching rhyming sentences and reinforcing them in subsequent lessons. Fourthly, in music lessons, each new element of knowledge is fully mastered in the course of the lesson, and it is widely practiced in the next lessons, turning it into permanent knowledge. In conclusion, in other words, general didactic principles of pedagogy are of great importance in the lessons of music culture and are of great importance in connecting music with life.

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